

ASSESSMENT TO THE LEVEL OF ORGANIZATIONAL READINESS FOR CHANGE IN PUBLIC DIRECTORATES IN ZAKHO INDEPENDENT ADMINISTRATION

¹DLOFAN AMIN SALMAN and ²RANJE MOHAMMAD NORI

^{1,2}Department of Management Science, College of Administration & Economy, University of Zakho, Kurdistan Region-Iraq.

Abstract

The aim of this study was to evaluate the level of readiness for change among directors and head of departments in public directorates that belong to “Zakho Independent Administration”. More specifically, the research focused on assessing selected dimensions of readiness for change, based on the (Holt et al., 2007) model. Namely; appropriateness, management support, self-Efficacy, and personally beneficial. One hundred and nine (109) directors and heads of departments were selected randomly from public directorates in Zakho. The participants were given a pre-structured questionnaire of two parts containing two parts. The first part was related to the demographic and personal characteristics. The second part was about the change readiness questionnaire by (Holt et al., 2007) four dimension model. Descriptive statistics were used to achieve research objectives from SPSS (24.0). The results exposed a moderate level of readiness for change as the mean for the overall change readiness was slightly above the midpoint of Five-point Likert scale (3.5 out of 5). Personally beneficial recorded the highest level among all the four dimensions. Whereas the lowest level was recorded with management support. Finally, the findings also showed that the level of readiness for change does not explain noticeable variance based on personal factors.

Introduction

The phenomena of globalization, which yielded a global competition, has greatly increased the frequency of change over the past few decades (Moric Milovanovic et al., 2022). Consequently, the process of organizational change has become an inevitable component of organizations' existence. It has been stated that the ability to quickly change and adjust to a new competitive environment is a crucial component of all organizations' survival (Rafferty et al., 2013; Todnem By, 2007). When organizations undergo a change process, employees have the option to either resist or adapt to the new circumstance. Therefore, studies on the individual readiness for change and change management have become more prevalent. Specially, after organizations started to face some difficulties such as; more frequent economic crises, increasing demand on public services, and extremely quick technological advancements.

In general, organizations constantly fail to shift quickly enough and sometimes they are unable to adapt to the new economic and social conditions in such a dynamic environment (Belak & Ušljebrika, 2014). In this regard, Burke, (2017) argued that every organization is impacted by different economic, social, political, legal, and other aspects. Thus, in order for organizations to properly run their operations, their leaders must continuously monitor and adjust to these variables. Moreover, they, sometimes, may just need to make small adjustments to their current economic model. However, some other times they may need to implement more dramatic

changes such as, new structures, new practices, or an entirely new identity. In order to "close the gap" with economic trends and adapt to environmental advancement, effective organizations need to have a strong plan of organizational change and change management. Organizational members -both leaders and followers- can determine how effectively organization can change with its surrounding variables (Moric Milovanovic et al., 2022). Therefore, the majority of staff and specifically those in power positions must be open to the change and ready for it in order to be implemented successfully. Otherwise, internal conflict may arise that might seriously harm the organization and fail any change efforts (Armenakis et al., 1993; Rafferty et al., 2013). Hence, the main purpose of this research is to investigate the degree to which individuals in leadership positions are ready to embrace organizational change. Based on the above discussion and clarifications, this study will answer the following question: "What is the level of readiness for organizational change among leaders in public directorates in Zakho District"

Research objectives:

This research aims specifically to achieve the following objectives:

- To evaluate the degree to which individuals in public directorates in "Zakho Independent Administration" believe that the organizational changes are appropriate.
- To investigate the extent to which individuals in public directorates in "Zakho Independent Administration" believe that they are capable of implementing organizational changes.
- To examine the degree to which individuals in public directorates in "Zakho Independent Administration" feel that the senior leaders support the organizational changes.
- To assess the extent to which individuals in public directorates in "Zakho Independent Administration" see that the organizational changes are personally beneficial.

Motivation to the Study

The constant developments within and across the different areas of political, economic, social, technical, legal, demographical, environmental, and global are putting pressure on organizations to adapt quickly to the upcoming changes in order to achieve success, growth and, in some cases, survival (Adam & Hanafi, 2022; and Chen et al., 2018). In addition to that, due to the intertwinement and integration of these areas, the scope of change has dramatically increased. For instance, the change that occurs in one domain may bring change to other domains as well. Hence, as stated by Rothwell & Sullivan, (2005) the only thing that is constant nowadays is change itself. Therefore, change is becoming an inevitable matter. Moreover, different reasons for change in the public sector have been proposed by researchers such as improving the quality of public services and increasing the well-being of society. In order to broaden the level of public services provided to Zakho people, Kurdistan Region Government (KRG) has recently announced Zakho Town as an independent administration from Duhok governorate and named it "Zakho Independent Administration". This transformation has

increased the quantity of the services provided by the local government in Zakho directorates. In addition, people's expectations of the quality of these services have also increased as a result of this massive change. However, the question that arises here is that, are the individuals working within these directorates, especially those with authority, ready to implement this change and meet people's expectations? Based on this question, this research tries to identify, via a descriptive study, the level of readiness for change among directors and head of debarments in public directorates in "Zakho Independent Administration". This is because individuals' readiness for change is one of the most significant element of the success or foliar of any change program (Ahmad et al., 2017; and Robbins & Coulter, 2017).

Readiness for Change

Readiness, as defined by Robbins & Coulter, (2017), is the willingness and ability of individuals to achieve a particular mission. An updated systematic review about organizational change readiness illustrated that, different terms have been used to define and measure readiness for change including willingness, preparedness for change, acceptance of change, openness to change and commitment to change (J. Meyer & Hamilton, 2013; Mignonac, 2008; Wanberg & Banas, 2000). Although the mentioned terms are slightly different in terms of meaning, they all express similar concepts. For instance, commitment to change is defined by Meyer & Hamilton, (2013) as employees' obligation to what is required for the change process to be implemented effectively. Likewise, openness to change is described by Wanberg & Banas, (2000) as a required condition to support the change efforts. Looking at the readiness for change as a cognitive state of resistance and support by individuals, it can be said that all the mentioned terms are similar since they are all supporting the change efforts to be successful.

Generally, change readiness is described as a combination of change commitment and change success. It expresses both the willingness to change and the common belief in the organization's ability to implement the change (Shea et al., 2014). Organizational readiness for change has been studied on different levels. For instance, according to Rafferty et al., (2013) readiness for change can be viewed on three different levels namely organizational level, group level, and individual level. Focusing on factors of the group and organizational level, change readiness contains collective efficacy, financial capabilities, and comprehensive attitude. While on the micro-level (i.e., individual level), readiness for change concentrates on studying and understanding individuals' characteristics in the organization and their attitude toward change programs. On the other hand, Weiner, (2009); and Adam & Hanafi, (2022) proposed two main forms of readiness for change including organizational and individual readiness. Due to the nature and objectives of this study, it is focusing on explaining the organizational readiness for change at the individual level.

Weiner, (2009) States that organizations face difficult issues at the individual level when they try to adopt changes. This could be traced back to the reason that not all organizational members are prepared and committed to change. Moreover, Robbins & Coulter, (2017) found that one of the main reasons behind the failure and success of any changing process is the individual's level of readiness for change. According to Mangundjaya, (2013); and Katsaros et al., (2020) organizational readiness for change at the individual level refers to the degree to

which employees within an organization are behaviorally, psychologically and mentally ready to accomplish a desirable change. Similarly, Hanpachern et al., (1998) illustrates that it is related to the individuals' attitudes, intentions and beliefs about the degree to which a specific change is accepted or rejected. They further added that readiness for change is a "state of mind about the need" of change. Armenakis et al., (1993) also defined readiness for change as individuals' beliefs, intentions and attitudes to reject or accept particular change efforts (i.e., the extent to which employees understand the necessity of the change for organization's success). They further added that, in order to implement change effectively, dealing properly with the issue of employees' readiness for change is more significant than utilizing a specific model of change. In this regard, a study on readiness for change by (Hanpachern et al., 1998) found that employees who have high level of change readiness are more likely to embrace change and can be more easily part of the change program. Hence, the next section will discuss the importance of individual readiness for change.

The Significant of Being Ready for Change

Accepting change is more than necessary for organizational growth since it is a constant and unavoidable process. Organizations need to develop strategies in order to prepare and encourage their employees for the continuous changes (Madsen et al., 2005). This is because a successful change implementation must be started with the workforce first. Numerous studies have revealed that most attempts to implement change in organization fail due to the resistance and unacceptance of the change programs by organizational members (Ján & Veronika, 2017). In this regard, evidence from previous studies highlight that 70% to 90% of change initiatives in organizations end up with failure (Beer & Nohria, 2000; and Decker et al., 2012). Although researchers traced this failure back to different reasons, yet employee resistance to organizational change is among the factors that are the most frequent reasons of organizational change initiatives failure (Stojanovic Aleksic et al., 2014; Lines et al., 2015). Repovš et al., (2019) also stated that change resistance is one of the primary causes of change efforts failure, which often arises as a result of the fear of the unknown situation that individuals may face after the implementation of change. They further claimed that, since people are "creatures of habit" and prefer routine, implementing change may make employees feel anxious and insecure and thereby show resistance. Hence, individuals must feel that dealing with change is a common occurrence. Therefore, in order for a change program to be willingly accepted and successfully implemented throughout the entire organization, it needs to be integrated with the organizational culture in a way that makes it more natural to the individuals and make them ready to accept it (Moric Milovanovic et al., 2022).

Moreover, Weiner, (2009) illustrated that, more successful change implementations are resulted from greater individual readiness for change. However, the question that arises here is how this could happen. According to Social cognitive theory by (Gist & Mitchell, 1992) employees are more likely to accept and involve in change initiatives when their level of organizational change readiness is high. For instance, they are more willing to implement new procedures, policies and practices. Adding to that, during the implementation of the change program, individuals with a high level of readiness for change are more likely to put in more

effort to support change and show greater persistence in the face of challenges. Furthermore, researchers proposed that individuals will support the change efforts and go above and beyond the call of duty or expectations of their roles when they are mentally, psychologically and behaviorally ready for change (J. Meyer & Hamilton, 2013; J. P. Meyer & Herscovitch, 2001). In this context, Hanpachern et al., (1998) explained that organizational members whose level of readiness for change is high are more likely to commit to and contribute to change initiatives. Herscovitch & Meyer, (2002) also support this idea and discovered that individuals who were committed to change because they “want to” instead of “need to” or “ought to” displayed not only cooperative behavior, yet they showed supporting behavior through promoting and sharing the values and benefits of the change programs to other organizational members.

To conclude, Studies by Armenakis et al., (1993); Madsen et al., (2005); Moric Milovanovic et al., (2022) have revealed that openness and acceptance of the change are indicators of a positive employee attitude toward change. A negative attitude, on the other hand, would typically lead to discontent, job delays, and very frequently to quitting and leaving the organization. Accordingly, it can be said that, in order for a change effort to be successfully implemented, organizational members must be attentive, open, and ready for it.

Methodology

Design

A descriptive study was conducted in Zakho Independent Administration in order to investigate the level of readiness for change among directors and head of departments in Zakho public directorates. The data collected quantitatively using a self-administered questionnaire for measuring readiness for change readiness.

Procedures

According to a decision by the ministry council of the Kurdistan Region Government, Zakho has become an independent administration. This decision has increased the number of the public directors in Zakho and expanded the services of the existing directorates. Therefore, the survey was conducted of the new opening directorates and the directorates that have been expanded due to the transformation process that happened in Zakho.

A self-administrated questionnaire was handed to (120) randomly selected directors and head of departments from various public directorates in Zakho Independent Administration-Kurdistan region-Iraq using probability sampling method; simple random sampling. Only (109) of them were returned properly. A letter was attached with the questionnaire explaining the purpose of the research and the confidentiality of the given information. The demographic factors and the personal characteristics are illustrated in the following table:

Table1: demographic factors and personal characteristics of the participants

N	Demographic and personal factors	Categories	N	Percentage
1	Gender	Male	78	71.6
		Female	31	28.4
2	Age	Under 30 years	8	7.3
		31 to 40 years	62	56.9
		41 to 50 years	34	31.2
		Above 50 years	5	4.6
3	Educational Level	Diploma	19	17.4
		Bachelor	82	75.2
		Master	3	2.8
4	Tenure	Less than 5 years	11	10.1
		5 to 10 years	25	22.9
		10 to 15 years	58	53.2
		More than 15 years	15	13.8
5	Position	Director	24	22.0
		Head of Departments	85	78.0

*Total respondents: 109

Table (1) demonstrates the demographic and personal factors of the participants. Regarding gender, the results showed that approximately 72% of the participants were male, whereas females consisted of nearly 28% of the whole participants. The results indicate that the number of women in power positions is quite few compared with men who occupy power positions. This could be traced back to the masculine nature of the society. It's also illustrated that different age levels participated in this survey. However, more than half of the respondents were from 31 to 40 years old. This indicates that most of the individuals who work in leadership positions in Zakho directorates are young. This could be considered a positive indicator for the local authority of Zakho to benefit from these young leaders and improve them for better missions in the future. In terms of educational level, although different levels of education can be noticed in the above table, yet the lion's share was taken by individuals with bachelor degrees with more than 75% of the entire participants. This means that most of the individuals in power positions are well educated and have the potential to be better leaders in the future if they were mentored properly. In addition to that, the above table demonstrates that approximately 54% of the participants were those who have 10 to 15 years of experience in leadership positions. Finally, out of 109 participants, 24 of them were the main directors which represent 22% of the whole research sample and 85 which represent 78% of them were head of departments within those directorates.

Measurement

A validated questionnaire developed by (Holt et al., 2007), was utilized in this study in order to assess the degree to which individuals in researched organizations are ready for organizational change. The questionnaire consisted of 25-items grouped into four key dimensions namely; Appropriateness (10-items), Change Efficacy (6-items), Management Support (6-items), and Personally Beneficial (3-items). Participants were supposed to rank each

item based on 5-point Likert-scale, (1-strongly disagree to 5-strongly agree), to express their level of agreement or disagreement with each statement. Regarding the reliability, (Holt et al., 2007) reported a high reliability for the scale as the coefficient Alphas for Appropriateness, Management Support, Change Efficacy, and personally beneficial were 0.80, 0.79, 0.79, and 0.66 respectively. For this research the Cronbach's Alpha for all items was 0.64 which refers to an acceptable reliability.

Data Analysis

In order to meet the research objectives, all primary data were quantitatively analyzed using SPSS (version 25.0). Descriptive statistics, including frequency, relative frequencies, central tendency measures, and measures of dispersion, were used to measure the level of readiness for change among directors and head of departments in Zakho public directorates.

Results

Table2: Levels of readiness for change dimensions among the researched sample

Items	Means	St. deviation
Appropriateness	3.5156	.34779
Management Support	3.4480	.39329
Change Efficacy	3.5872	.38530
Personal Beneficiary	3.6911	.62969
Overall Readiness for Change	3.5605	.25437

Table (2) explains the level of readiness for change and its dimensions including; Appropriateness, Management Support, Change Efficacy, and Personal Beneficiary among directors and head of department in “Zakho Independent Administration” directorates. All the mean values in the above table are slightly above the midpoint of the 5-point Likert scale. This indicates that the directors and head of departments in Zakho public directorates showed a moderate level of readiness for change. More specifically, the highest mean value was for “Personally Beneficial” with approximately (3.7). This indicates that individuals who work in leadership positions within the public directorates in Zakho, see that the organizational changes are personally beneficial for them. Followed by “Change Efficacy” and “Appropriateness” with nearly (3.6) and (3.5) respectively. This shows that, to some extent, these leaders believe that they are capable of implementing organizational changes and admit that the organizational changes are appropriate. Although the mean value for “Management Support” was above the mid-point of the 5-point Likert scale with roughly (3.4), yet it recorded the lowest mean compared to the other three dimensions of readiness for change. This refers to the fact that people who work in power positions in the research directorates feel that the senior leaders’ support for the organizational changes does not meet their expectations. Finally, it can be stated that directors and heads of departments in the researched directorates are to some extent ready for organizational change, as the recorded mean value is slightly above the mid-point of the 5-point Likert scale with roughly (3.5). Additionally, the standard deviation values for Appropriateness, Management Support, Change Efficacy, and Personal Beneficiary and overall

readiness of change were (0.347, 0.393, 0.385, 0.629 and 0.254), respectively, which refer to a low level of variation of the responses to the studied variables.

Table3: Levels of overall readiness for change based on Demographic and personal factors

Demographic and personal factors	Categories	Mean	St. deviation
Gender	Male	3.57	0.26251
	Female	3.53	0.23503
Age	Under 30 years	3.49	0.28976
	31 to 40 years	3.59	0.24134
	41 to 50 years	3.51	0.28148
	Above 50 years	3.56	0.14642
Educational Level	Diploma	3.48	0.24548
	Bachelor	3.56	0.22228
	Master	3.78	0.16080
Tenure	Less than 5 years	3.47	0.27692
	5 to 10 years	3.54	0.21616
	10 to 15 years	3.60	0.25685
	More than 15 years	3.58	0.23777
Current Position	Director	3.55	0.17568
	Head of Departments	3.56	0.27334

Table (3) explain the variance in the level of readiness for change among directors and head of departments in the researched directorates in Zakho based on the differences in personal characteristics namely; gender, age, educational level, tenure, and position. Although statistically there was not big variance based on these characteristics, yet, some minor variance can be seen in the above table. A slight difference was found between males and females in terms of their level of readiness for change. Males have shown to be more ready for the upcoming changes than females. Regarding the age groups, there was also a small difference among age groups and the highest level of change readiness was shown by those who are between 31 to 40 years old. This is a good indicator as this age group represents more than half of the researched sample in the current study (see table 2). In terms of educational level, results from the above table have revealed that, people with higher degrees have shown greater level of readiness for change. This indicates that, the higher an individuals' educational attainment is, the more likely they are to embrace and accept change. A slight difference was also found based on the years of experience. However, the highest level of readiness for change were found among those Individuals with 10-15 years of experience, which represents more than half of the researched sample (see table 2). Finally, no variance was found based on the position as both the directors and head of departments showed almost the same level of readiness.

Figure 1: Data distribution

Figure (1) depicts the distribution of overall averages of the respondents on the X axis and the frequency of the participants on the Y axis. In general, despite having some outliers (skewed to the left), the overall averages of the respondents on the X axis showed to be normally distributed. In addition, the figure also showed that the overall mean was (3, 56) with Std. Dev. (0.25). This indicates a moderate level of readiness for change among the researched sample. Moreover, The Std. Dev. value refers to a low level of variation of the responses to the studied variables.

Discussion

The purpose of this study was to assess the level of readiness for change among individuals who occupy leadership positions in public directorates in “Zakho Independent Administration”. More specifically, the study focused mainly on evaluating four key dimensions of readiness for change namely appropriateness, management support, change efficacy, and personally beneficial. Utilizing a standardized questionnaire, which is one of the widely used instruments for assessing readiness for change, have provided an understanding into a culture that has not been previously studied in the readiness for change literature.

Different dimensions have been studied by researchers for determining individual readiness for change including; participating in; promoting; and resisting change (Hanpachern et al., 1998) change commitment and change efficacy (Weiner, 2009) emotional readiness, intentional readiness, and cognitive readiness (Bouckenooghe et al., 2009) and discrepancy, appropriateness, efficacy, principal support, and valence (Armenakis et al., 2007). Krieger, (1996) also provided a good understanding about strengths and weaknesses of change readiness. This was through measuring the degree of optimism, adventurousness, confidence, resourcefulness, tolerance for ambiguity, and adaptability that individuals have to be ready for change. The present study has utilized the (Holt et al., 2007) which claimed that

appropriateness, management support, change efficacy, and personally beneficial are main determinants of individuals' readiness for change.

Findings from the current research illustrate a moderate level of readiness for change among the directors and head of departments in Zakho public directorates with all four dimensions. The highest level was recorded with "Personally Beneficial" dimension. This indicates that individuals who work in leadership positions within the public directorates in Zakho, see that the organizational changes are personally beneficial for them. This attributes to the individuals' beliefs that the upcoming change initiatives are not threats to their current status in the organization, will not negatively affect their personal relationships, and their future will not be limited due to these changes (Holt et al., 2007). Both "Change Efficacy" and "Appropriateness" have shown moderate levels of readiness. This means that individuals in the researched directorates see that they are capable of implementing organizational changes and admit that the organizational change initiatives are appropriate. This is attributed to the individuals' beliefs in the skills that they have for implementing the upcoming changes and the experience they obtained from previous change efforts. Alongside with their beliefs about the necessity of adopting organizational changes and the benefits that the organization could obtain from these changes. "Management Support" has recorded the lowest level of readiness compared to the other dimensions. This indicates that directors and heads of department in the researched directorates do not believe that the senior leaders support the organizational changes initiatives as required in order to be implemented successfully. This is attributed to the lack of encouragement to embrace change and absence of motivation to implement it properly. Finally, The findings of this study are in line with the findings of (Moric Milovanovic et al., 2022) in Croatian construction companies, (Harrison, 2017) in South Africa, and (Workeneh & Abebe, 2019) in an Ethiopian university, and (Olafsen et al., 2021) who also found a moderate level of readiness for change among individuals in Norwegian public organizations undergoing major strategic changes. This indicates that individuals may need to be prepared for change and be trained of the upcoming changes. In this concern, (Hanpachern et al., 1998) suggested that in order for the process of implementing change to be completed successfully human resources must be developed to embrace change before trying to implement it.

Conclusion

The present study evaluated the level of readiness for change among directors and heads of departments in public directorates that belong to "Zakho Independent Administration". More precisely, the study tried to explore the degree to which these individuals, who occupy leadership positions, see that upcoming organizational changes and initiatives are appropriate. Furthermore, it explained the extent to which these individuals see the top management support change efforts. It also identified the degree to which they believe that they are capable of adapting to the new situation. Lastly, it explained the degree to which they think that future status will be personally beneficial. The empirical results discovered that managers and heads of departments in the researched directorates are partially ready for organizational change. In addition to that, the results also revealed that, statistically, demographic factors do not show variance in the level of readiness for change

Limitation and Further Studies

The present study has some limitations including:

1. Various dimensions have been presented by researchers to measure readiness for change. The present research has used the four dimensions model proposed by (Holt et al., 2007). Therefore, it's recommended that future studies may use some other dimensions for this purpose.
2. This research was conducted among individuals who work in leadership positions, future studies may include ordinary employees who are dealing directly with the stakeholders.
3. Due to the time limit, the sample used in the present study was small. It is suggested for the future studies to include a larger sample, which may give a better reflection of the level of readiness among the researched population.
4. The aim is to identify only the level of change readiness. It is highly suggested for future studies to investigate the factors that affect individual readiness for change or the outcomes of being a ready person for change.

Recommendations

Through the discussion of the literature of readiness for change, it was found that one of the main tools of implementing change programs successfully is to have ready individuals for change. In addition, the empirical results from the current study have identified a moderate level of readiness for change at the researched directorates among the directors and head of departments. Therefore, for the change programs to be successfully implemented in Zakho public directorates, the researchers recommended the following procedures:

1. The local authority in “Zakho Independent Administrations” has to work continuously on preparing a suitable environment that fits with the desired change.
2. Explaining the necessity of the change programs to the people in public directorates through increasing their consciousness about the upcoming changes in order to make them look at the change as an appropriate step.
3. Preparing the opportunity of having continuous planned training, mentoring, and coaching programs for those who are in power in order to be capable of implementing change initiatives successfully.
4. Senior leaders and the top level of management, in Kurdistan Region generally and “Zakho Independent Administration” precisely, have to support the organizational change in order to make the lower level of management that they have sufficient support to implement change.
5. Change programs must be created in a manner that makes the practitioners feel and realize that the organizational changes are personally beneficial for them.

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